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Effects of reverberation on speech intelligibility in noise for hearing-impaired listeners

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Reverberation can have a strong detrimental effect on speech intelligibility in noise. Two main monaural effects are studied here: the temporal smearing of the target speech, which makes the speech less understandable, and the temporal smearing of the noise, which reduces the opportunity for listening in the masker dips. These phenomena have been shown to affect normal-hearing (NH) listeners. The aim of this study is to understand whether hearing-impaired (HI) listeners are more affected by reverberation, and if so to identify which of these two effects is responsible. They will be investigated separately and in combination, by applying reverberation either on the target speech, on the noise masker, or on both sources. Binaural effects will not be investigated here. Intelligibility scores in the presence of stationary and modulated noise will be systematically compared for both NH and HI listeners in these situations.

1. Introduction

In our daily lives we often experience situations where we have to understand speech hindered by an interfering noise. In these conditions reverberation can greatly decrease our speech understanding abilities. This study aims to better understand how reverberation could affect intelligibility for hearing-impaired (HI) listeners. This should allow to understand more precisely which acoustic conditions are detrimental to them and, in the long term, it could help to improve the acoustic regulations related to room design. For example, if the speech intelligibility of HI listeners is reduced at lower

levels of reverberation compared to normal-hearing (NH) listeners, more restrictive reverberation limits could be recommended in public buildings.

Speech intelligibility in a noisy environment depends on several factors [1,2] that can be influenced by reverberation. It has been shown that in a room the envelope of the sound can be temporally smeared, depending of the level of reverberation [3], due to the individual soundpaths with various time delays taken by the sound reflections. The temporal smearing of the target speech has been shown to reduce its intelligibility [4,5]. When speech is heard in the presence of an interfering noise, speech intelligibility increases if the noise is modulated in amplitude [6]. NH listeners seem to be able to benefit from the "gaps" in the modulated noise to better understand the target speech. This benefit is often called "dip listening advantage", "benefit of listening in the gaps", or "fluctuating masker benefit". In a room, the dip listening benefit seems to be less important because reverberation fills in the masker gaps. For example, a recent study measured speech reception thresholds (SRTs, sound level of the target compared to the one of the interferer to recognize 50% of the words) for NH listeners with interfering noises and different degrees of reverberation applied to the noise [7]. The noise was either stationary or modulated using various speech envelopes, while reverberation was changed by varying the distance between the noise source and the listener. When increasing reverberation was applied to a modulated noise, the dip-listening benefit was significantly reduced. In addition to these two monaural mechanisms, it has been shown that speech intelligibility is improved when the noise source is at a different position than the target speaker, thanks to our binaural system [8]. This advantage from binaural hearing is also reduced by reverberation [9,10]. As a starting point, the present study will focus on the two monaural effects of reverberation, so that binaural effects will not be investigated here. It has also been shown that auditory stream segregation and attentional effects are less affected by reverberation [11]. These effects will not be studied here. Since they can be very important with speech interferers, only noise interferers will be used in the present study.

A few previous studies have compared the monaural effects of reverberation for NH and HI listeners. Duquesnoy and Plomp (1980) tested one group of NH listeners and four groups of HI listeners with different degrees of hearing loss [12]. When increasing the level of reverberation as measured by the reverberation time (RT), from 0 s to 2.3 s, the SRTs of the NH listeners increased by 10 dB. The SRTs of the most severely impaired HI listeners increased by 18 dB when going from RT = 0 s to RT = 1 s. However, since the study had a different aim, the effect of reverberation on SRTs was not statistically analysed, so the significance of the effect remains unknown.

Helfer and Wilber (1990) tested four groups of listeners, old and young NH and HI listeners, at four different RTs, with and without noise [13]. Overall, this study reported a decrease in intelligibility scores (the percentage of words correctly identified) for all groups when reverberation increased and a significant interaction between the group of listeners and the reverberation time. In more details, applying reverberation to both the target speech and the noise (cafeteria noise) decreased the intelligibility scores by 20 % for the NH groups and by 25 % for the HI groups. Both temporal smearing of the target and a reduction in dip listening could account for these results. An additional condition without masking noise also evidenced a detrimental effect of reverberation with a 10 % drop in intelligibility for the NH listeners and a 20 % drop for the HI listeners. However, when expressed into percentage, the results can be biased by floor and ceiling effects. To correct this, it is necessary to convert the scores into rationalised arcsine units (RAUs) [14,15]. When the scores from Helfer and Wilber (1990) are converted into RAUs, the differences between groups seem reduced. NH listeners have intelligibility decreases of 22 RAUs and 20 RAUs for the "speech in noise" and the "speech in quiet" condition respectively, while the HI listeners have intelligibility decreases of 28 RAUs and 25 RAUs. This study did not investigate at which reverberation level speech intelligibility decreased the most for the different groups.

Harris and Swenson (1990) compared a group of NH listeners with two groups of HI listeners: one group with mild hearing loss and another group with severe hearing loss [16]. In this study, intelligibility scores were measured at three levels of reverberation, in the presence of a stationary

noise. The results showed that reverberation caused a larger decrease in scores for the HI groups (30 % decrease for the HI groups against 20 % decrease for the NH group). They also found that HI listeners were more affected than NH listeners for lower RTs. The intelligibility decrease for RTs increasing from 0 s to 0.5 s was equal to 10 % for the NH listeners against 20 % for the HI listeners. The intelligibility decrease for RTs increasing from 0.5 s to 1.5 s was equal to 12 % for the NH listeners and 8 % for the HI listeners. Since the interfering noise was stationary, no listening in the gap was involved in any condition and it can be assumed that the effect of reverberation was restricted to the effect of target smearing. This could imply that HI listeners are more affected by temporal smearing than NH listeners. This could also indicate that HI listeners are affected at lower reverberation levels, compared to NH listeners. However these results could also be partly explained by a ceiling effect: when the intelligibility scores are converted in RAUs, the intelligibility decrease when the RT increases from 0 s to 1.5 s is of 28 RAUs for the NH listeners and 32 RAUs for the HI listeners. Between 0 s and 0.5 s, the intelligibility decrease is of 15 RAUs for the NH listeners and 22 RAUs for the HI listeners. These results are also not consistent with another study, which tested NH and HI listeners at two low reverberation levels (RT = 0.25 s and 0.5 s) [17]. Both groups had significantly lower intelligibility scores at the higher reverberation level. However, while the NH group had better performances overall, the intelligibility decrease was more important for the NH group than for the HI group (29 RAUs and 16 RAUs, respectively). This inconsistency between the two studies could perhaps be linked to the difference in the hearing losses tested: the former study had two HI groups with a medium hearing loss of 30 dB and 60 dB respectively, while the latter study had HI listeners with heterogeneous hearing loss ranging from 13 dB to 70 dB. It could also come from a difference in room geometry and/or source distances. Both studies used rooms of similar sizes (11.92 m³ [16] and 13.6 m³ [17]) but the first room had nonparallel walls while the second had parallel walls. Unfortunately, the direct to reverberant energy ratios (DRRs) were not provided in these studies, so nothing can be concluded here. It is also worth to note that the first study had a total of 30 listeners (10 NH listeners and 20 HI listeners) while the second only had 12 (5 NH listeners and 7 HI listeners). It remains unclear whether HI listeners are more affected by reverberation than NH listeners and at which reverberation levels they are affected the most. Many of the differences between NH and HI listeners reported in the literature have not been verified by statistical tests and could have been biased by ceiling effects.

To the best of our knowledge the decrease of dip listening benefit caused by reverberation in the case of HI listeners has only been investigated by one study [18]. However the HI listeners did not have much dip listening benefit, even in the anechoic condition, and no statistical test was done regarding this particular interaction. It is still possible to make some assumptions, based on numerous studies on dip listening benefit for HI listeners without reverberation. When tested at different signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs, sound level of the target compared to the one of the interferer) providing comparable SRTs for NH and HI listeners, HI listeners generally have very poor dip listening benefit. For example, Bernstein and Grant (2009) have estimated SRTs for 20 NH and 20 HI listeners with various types of masker (stationary noise, modulated noise, competing voice) [19]. They found that the NH SRTs were 4-8 dB lower with a modulated noise compared to a stationary noise, while HI listeners did not benefit at all from the masker modulations. This seems to imply that HI listeners cannot rely on dip listening as much as NH listeners do. Hall and al. (2012) measured the SRTs of NH and HI listeners using stationary and temporally modulated noises [20]. They found a significantly higher dip listening benefit for the NH listeners. Lorenzi and al. (2006) measured consonant identification scores of NH and HI listeners using noise maskers with amplitude modulation rates varying from 2 Hz to 128 Hz [21]. They found no dip listening benefit for half of the HI listeners, while the other half had a smaller benefit when compared to the NH listeners.

The reduced dip listening benefit of HI listeners could be partly due to the SNRs at which they were tested. It has been shown that the dip listening benefit depends on the SNR at which it is measured: when the SNR rises, the dip listening benefit decreases [22]. When tested at the same

SNR (thus generally not at the same intelligibility performance), NH and HI listeners have much more comparable dip listening benefit [19]. Further studies controlled for the effect of SNR on dip listening. One tested HI and NH listeners at frequencies at which they have similar hearing thresholds and found no significant difference in dip listening benefit between groups [23]. In another study the HI listeners were tested with a closed set procedure while the NH listeners were tested with an open set procedure [24]. The scores from the NH listeners were reduced a lot and both groups had similar scores at the same SNRs. Since the main goal of this study was to study the effects of supra-threshold deficits on the dip listening benefit, the audibility of both groups was equalized by filtering the stimuli, to eliminate the elements below the hearing thresholds of the HI listeners. This study found no significant difference in dip listening benefit between groups, except at a high modulation rate (32 Hz). They concluded that when HI listeners were not impaired by their reduced audibility, they were able to benefit from dip listening, except at high modulation rates where they might be hindered by a reduced temporal resolution.

If HI listeners can at least partly benefit from dip listening, it is relevant to assume that HI listeners might be affected by the decrease of dip listening caused by reverberation. Studies which measured the intelligibility scores of HI and NH listeners with square-wave modulated noise might provide some insights to test for this hypothesis. For example, George and al. (2006) have tested the effect of various duty cycles (ie. the fraction of time period during which the noise is present) upon intelligibility [25]. The reduction of this duty cycle can be seen as a basic representation of the width reduction of the noise gaps caused by reverberation. It appeared that HI listeners had lower scores overall and the score decrease caused by the duty cycle reduction was more important for the NH listeners. This could indicate that HI listeners do not benefit as much from dip listening as NH listeners do, and thus the effect of reverberation on the dip listening benefit might be more important for NH listeners than for HI listeners.

The aim of the present study is to better understand the effect of reverberation on speech intelligibility in noise for HI listeners. The effects of target temporal smearing and the reduction in dip listening will be addressed separately as well as in combination, for both HI and NH listeners. Based on the literature, this study aims to test the following hypotheses:

- (i) Hypothesis 1: the temporal smearing of the speech caused by reverberation impairs more HI listeners than NH listeners.
- (ii) Hypothesis 2: reverberation affects the dip listening benefit more for NH listeners than for HI listeners.
- (iii) Hypothesis 3-1: the overall (monaural) effect of reverberation impairs HI listeners as much as NH listeners.

In addition to these three main hypotheses, this study also aims to test several secondary ones:

- (i) Hypothesis 1-1: the temporal smearing of the target speech impairs intelligibility at lower levels of reverberation for HI listeners compared to NH listeners (that is to say HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at low RTs).
- (ii) Hypothesis 1-2: at high levels of reverberation, HI listeners are more impaired than NH listeners by the temporal smearing of the speech (that is to say, HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at high RTs).
- (iii) Hypothesis 3-2-a: In the case of NH listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise.
- (iv) Hypothesis 3-2-b: In the case of HI listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise.

To test these hypotheses, it is necessary to measure speech intelligibility for HI and NH listeners, applying reverberation either only on the target speech, only on the interfering noise, or on both sources, as previously done for NH listeners [26]. This allows to address separately the effects of reverberation on the temporal smearing of the target and the reduction in dip listening. Care

should also be taken to assure that the dip listening benefit is evaluated at comparable SNRs for HI and NH listeners.

2. Methods

(a) Listeners

The NH listeners will need to have audiometric thresholds better than or equal to 20 dB hearing level from 250 Hz to 4000 Hz and better than or equal to 25 dB hearing level from 6000 to 8000 Hz in at least one ear. The best ear will be selected for testing. To be included in the HI group, listeners will need to have a moderate sensorineural hearing loss (around 30-60 dB dB in the 250-4000 Hz range) with no significant air-bone gap (≤ 10 dB). The ear with the closer audiometric specifications will be selected. Participants will be aged between 18 and 70 years old. Furthermore, since it has been shown that the detrimental effect of reverberation can be dependent on the age of the listeners [13,27], the HI and NH listeners will be matched as much as possible in age, in order to limit this confounding effect.

The study has received a formal agreement from a French national ethic committee (CPP Ile de France X, protocol #05-2019). The listeners will sign an informed consent and will be paid an hourly wage for their participation.

(b) Stimuli

A matrix-style closed-set speech material will be used. It allows to prepare as many sentences as required for the large number of conditions to be tested, from a limited number of words. At the same time, the difficulty across sentences is rather uniform for such material, unlike in open-set tests where difficulty can vary substantially across sentences. This minimizes variability due to the materials, which might otherwise contribute to the variability across individuals and tested conditions that are of primary interest here. The words from the French Matrix test (FrMatrix) will be used [28]. This closed test consists of five groups of ten words: ten names, ten verbs, ten numerals, ten objects and ten colors. These words can be arranged to form various sentences, for example "Agnès attrape cinq crayons jaunes" (Agnès catches five yellow pencils) or "Etienne déplace six jetons bleus" (Etienne moves six blue chips). The number of words recognized by the listener is then measured. The words were chosen so that they best represent French mean phonetic distribution. Jansen and al. (2012) created 280 sentences with these words. The recording was done in a way that allowed to preserve the coarticulation between each word. The sound levels of the words were homogenized so that there is equal intelligibility across words, sentences and test lists. To preserve this equalisation in the experiment, only the mean level of the sentences was varied. The 50 words composing the test can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Words of the FrMatrix test [28]

Name	Verb	Numeral	Object	Color
Agnès	achète	deux	anneaux	blancs
Charlotte	attrape	trois	ballons	bleus
Emile	demande	cinq	classeurs	bruns
Etienne	déplace	six	crayons	gris
Eugène	dessine	sept	jetons	jaunes
Félix	propose	huit	livres	mauves
Jean-Luc	ramasse	neuf	pions	noirs
Julien	ramène	onze	piquets	roses
Michel	reprend	douze	rubans	rouges
Sophie	voudrait	quinze	vélos	verts

To study the effect of reverberation on the dip listening benefit, two types of noise will be tested: a stationary noise and a modulated noise. The dip listening benefit will be estimated as the score difference between the condition with modulated noise and the condition with stationary noise at a given SNR.

For the modulated noise, several semantically unpredictable sentences from another speech material [29] were used to create two-voice vocoded speech. The use of this speech material allows to have less predictable gaps than with the sentences of the FrMatrix, which all have the same structure and length. A 3-channel vocoder was used, with an envelope low-pass filter-cut off frequency of 60 Hz [30]. The vocoded speech was filtered so that it has the same long-term spectrum as the target sentences. Speech modulations will be tested instead of artificial modulations (such as sinusoidally modulated noise), to avoid any effect of the predictability of the gaps in the masker [7].

The stationary noise was created by concatenating the same semantically unpredictable sentences, so that it has the same spectrum as the modulated noise. The Fourier transform of the signal was calculated, its phase was randomized and the inverse Fourier transform was taken [7]. The stationary noise was filtered so that it has the same long-term spectrum as the target sentences.

Random excerpts of this noise were selected and gated on and off with 10-ms raised-cosine ramps. Each excerpt is one second longer and begins between 300 and 700 ms before the target sentence, the exact delay being randomly selected on each trial.

To add reverberation to the noise and/or to the target speech, several monaural room impulse responses (RIRs) were artificially generated using the software CATT-acoustic (v9.1). This software enables to simulate the sound reaching a microphone from a source, with the source and microphone simulated at any positions within the room, with adjustable geometric and acoustic properties of the walls, ceiling and floor. The room was created with the following dimensions: 5 m x 9 m x 2.7 m. The source was placed at 1.75 m from the 5-m wall and 3.75 m from the 9-m wall. The listener was placed at 3.25 m from the 5-m wall and 5 m of the 9-m wall. These positions were chosen so that the source and listener were close to each other and far away from the corners of the room. Both sources were placed at a height of 1.5 m to simulate standing persons. To control the reverberation level using a single parameter, the floor, ceiling and all the walls were given the same frequency-dependent absorption coefficient of mineral wool. To increase the reverberation level to reach a given broadband RT, these coefficients were decreased simultaneously in all frequency bands by division. With this configuration, the only varying parameter is the absorption coefficient of the rooms. This allows a great control of the reverberation: between each RIR only the reflections changes, preserving the relative level differences across reflections. All the RIRs were normalized in energy, so that convolution does not introduce broadband level differences across reverberation conditions.

Modulation analyses were done to determine which RTs were interesting to test. The modulation spectra of the noise and speech signals were generated by computing the envelope of the signal, dividing this envelope by its mean and calculating its power spectrum in octave bands between 1 and 16 Hz [7]. They appear in Figure 1 and Figure 2. The peak that can sometimes be observed at low frequencies is due to an artifact inherent to the room simulation program. This DC component increasing with the level of reverberation is not audible, and it was not taken into account for the level equalisation. It appears there is little difference in modulation level for the two lowest RTs (anechoic, 0.15 s) for the speech signals. Above RT = 0.15 s, when reverberation increases the speech signals show a decrease in modulation level. Due to these results, it was decided to test all the RTs above 0.15. Instead of testing the anechoic condition, only the RT = 0.15 s value was kept, so that all the signals were convoluted with BRIRs varying only due to a single parameter (the gain applied to the absorption coefficients of the room). For the noise signals the hypotheses only study the presence of an interaction of reverberation, and only two extreme BRIRs are needed. As a result, only the RT = 0.15 s and RT = 1.5 s values were used with the noise

signals. The Figure 2 shows a decrease of modulation level with increasing reverberation for these conditions. The acoustic properties of the artificial rooms tested are presented in Table 2.

Figure 1. Modulation spectra of the anechoic speech and of the speech signals convoluted with the RIRs of the artificial rooms.

Figure 2. Modulation spectra of the modulated and stationary noises convoluted with RIRs of rooms with the two extreme RTs.

The mean presentation level of the speech sentences will be fixed at 50 dB SPL and the noise level will be adapted to reach the desired SNRs.

(c) Procedure

All the listening tests will be done monaurally in a sound proof booth (sound attenuation over 70 dB from 100 Hz to 20 kHz) with headphones (Sennheiser HD 250 Linear II). All sound levels will be calibrated with an artificial ear associated with a flat coupler (Larson Davis AEC101 and 824).

Table 2. RTs (in s), DRR and absorption coefficients (α , in %) of the simulated rooms

RT	DRR	α (125 Hz)	α (250 Hz)	α (500 Hz)	α (1 kHz)	α (2 kHz)	α (4 kHz)
0.15	10.7	58	69	96	97	99	91
0.5	-6.05	17.4	20.7	28.8	29.1	29.7	27.3
0.8	-8.97	8.7	10.35	14.4	14.55	14.85	13.65
1.1	-11.0	5.8	6.9	9.6	9.7	9.9	9.1
1.5	-12.21	3.77	4.485	6.24	6.305	6.435	5.915

The stimuli on each trial will be the five words of the target sentence and an interfering noise at a given SNR. On each trial, listeners will choose an answer for each of the five words. These choices will be made by selecting among all the possible words presented on a computer screen in front of them. The matrix tests are often used with twenty sentences that use twice the fifty words of the speech set to measure the SRT [28]. In this experiment, to avoid the confounding effect of SNR on the dip listening benefit [22], it was decided to measure the intelligibility scores at five SNRs for each listener. For each listener and condition, psychometric function will then be fitted to the results, with the `psignifit` toolbox [31]. For each tested SNR, listeners will listen to ten sentences that will contain the fifty words of the FrMatrix (in other words, for each condition fifty sentences will be tested to obtain the psychometric function). The words layout and the tested conditions will be selected in random order on a sentence-by-sentence basis.

It is necessary to assure that there is at least one common SNR for all listeners that allows for a dip listening effect and at the same time that there are no floor or ceiling effect for the two groups at this SNR. To insure the existence of such a SNR, HI listeners will have linear frequency-dependent gain applied to the stimuli before presentation. This gain will be set on an individual basis according to the NAL-RP prescription rule [32]. This linear amplification allows to partly compensate for the audibility loss and should insure that the score difference at a same SNR is not too large between the HI and NH groups. It was decided to not completely equalize the audibility of the HI and NH listeners, in order to not focus only on the supra-threshold elements of the hearing loss. This method allows to avoid the confounding effect of SNR without being affected by floor and ceiling effect. At the same time it still allows to test for a difference of audibility between HI and NH listeners.

The NAL-RP amplification can increase the sound level by up to 20 dB for the severe HI listeners. This can lead to stimuli with a sound level of 90-100 dB; To make sure that the stimuli are not uncomfortable for HI listeners, a loudness test will be done at the beginning of the experiment, with a method similar to the Contour test presented by Cox and al. (1997) [33]. The listeners will be submitted to a stimuli and will have to evaluate its loudness on a 7-point scale: 1-very soft, 2-soft, 3-comfortable but slightly soft, 4-comfortable, 5-comfortable but slightly loud, 6-loud, but O.K., 7-uncomfortably loud. The sound level of the stimuli will be raised by steps of 5 dBs until the listener finds the stimuli uncomfortably loud. If it is necessary SNR range of the experiment will then be adjusted so that the listener is not tested above this upper limit.

The low presentation level used in this experiment limits the risks of discomfort. However, it raises the question of the audibility of the sentences. To make sure that they are audible in quiet, an audibility test will be done at the beginning of the experiment. It will consist of a list of 20 sentences in quiet. If the audibility scores of the listener are below 90 %, the presentation level will be raised.

Each listening session will be preceded by a practice test consisting of two 20-sentence lists, so that listeners get familiar with the task and to limit the short term training effect that comes with a closed-set speech test [28]. There also seems to be a training effect on the long term, across multiple sessions [34]. It does not seem possible to compensate for this effect, since no study determined the training effect for this speech set in terms of intelligibility percentages for the SNRs that are planned in this experiment. This should add some noise to the measures but should not affect too much the differences measured between conditions, since they are randomly tested

at different moments of the experiment. Another drawback of matrix speech sets is that they seem less affected by reverberation than daily life speech [35]. Such an effect cannot be compensated and will be addressed in more details in the discussion.

(d) Tested conditions

To test the hypotheses of this study, three ways of applying reverberation to the stimuli will be tested for each listener: one with reverberation applied to both speech and noise (both temporal smearing and a decrease in dip listening could impair intelligibility), one with reverberation applied only to the speech (only temporal smearing could contribute to the results) and one with reverberation applied only to the noise (only a decrease in dip listening could contribute to the results). For each reverberation condition, different RTs will be tested, for both noise modulations (stationary, speech modulated). These conditions are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Conditions tested in the present study

Application of reverberation	Speech only	Noise only	Speech and noise
Underlying mechanism tested	Temporal smearing	Dip Listening	Both
RTs	0.15 s, 0.5 s, 0.8 s, 1.1 s, 1.5 s	0.15 s, 1.5 s	0.15 s, 1.5 s

The condition with reverberation applied only to the speech target will test the hypothesis that temporal smearing reduces speech intelligibility at low RTs for HI listeners and at higher RTs for NH listeners. To do so, it is necessary to test more RTs for this condition. Based on previous work [16] and the modulation analyses, the following RTs were selected: 0.15 s, 0.5 s, 0.8 s, 1.1 s, 1.5 s. Two noise modulations will be tested. Reverberation will be applied only to the target, so that dip listening is not affected [7].

The condition with reverberation applied only to the noise will test for an interaction between the groups of listeners (HI vs NH), the presence of noise modulations and the level of reverberation. The idea here is to test whether the dip listening benefit is affected differently by reverberation for the two groups of listeners. Since this hypothesis studies the presence of an interaction, the two types of noise will only be tested at the two extreme RTs. For this condition, reverberation will only be applied to the interfering noise, so that there is no temporal smearing of the target speech.

The condition with reverberation applied to both sources will test the hypothesis that reverberation (overall) does not affect differently NH and HI listeners. Similarly to the condition with reverberation applied to the noise, this hypothesis studies the presence of an interaction, and only the two extreme levels of reverberation (RTs of 0.15 s, and 1.5 s) will be applied simultaneously to noise and speech. Two noise modulations will be tested.

Each combination of reverberation condition \times RT \times noise modulation will be tested at five SNRs in order to measure the full psychometric function of the participants. This makes a total of 70 conditions. Each condition will be measured in approximately 120 seconds (12 seconds per sentence), which makes a total of two hours and twenty minutes for the whole experiment. The experiment will be done in three sessions of one hour and 15 minutes, in order to have the time to measure the audiograms and realize the loudness, audibility and training tests. In order to avoid risks of memorization of the tested conditions — SNR, RT, masker modulation, reverberation condition — will be selected in random order on a sentence-by-sentence basis.

(e) Data analysis

(i) Statistical analyses

Before any statistical analysis, all intelligibility scores will first be transformed into Rationalized Arcsine Units (RAUs) [14]. All the analyses will be done at a single common SNR of the psychometric curves of the listeners. This SNR will be chosen so that ceiling and floor effects are kept to a minimum. Our analyses primarily rely on Bayesian ANOVAs. Bayesian tests not only allow to show evidence for the presence of an effect, but also for its absence, something that frequentist tests do not permit [36]. In our case, this will be particularly useful to study the interaction of dip listening and reverberation, for which it is more difficult to anticipate whether there will be differences between the HI and NH groups. This will also allow to study the hypothesis 3-1, for which we intend to show an absence of effect.

Five Bayesian-mixed-design-repeated-measures ANOVAs are planned, one for each reverberation condition (applied to speech, to noise, or to both) and two others that study the NH and HI listeners separately. We estimated that there was not enough information to use informative priors and decided to use a Cauchy prior distribution as a default prior, with a scale value of 1/2 [37]. Indeed, as explained above, to the best of our knowledge there is no clear evidence to confirm or infirm hypotheses 1, 1-1, 1-2, 2, 3-2-a and 3-2-b. There are some studies that seem to contradict hypothesis 3-1, but they might be misleading due to the use of percentage scores instead of RAUs scores.

The three ANOVAs related to the three reverberation conditions will have one between-group factor (HI vs NH) and two within-group factors (RT and noise modulation). For each of these Bayesian ANOVAs, the Bayes factor comparing the model with the interaction studied (RT x group or RT x group x noise) and without it will be calculated. The two ANOVAs related to the listeners group will only have two within-group factors (RT and noise modulation). A Bayes factor superior to 10 will be considered as a strong evidence for the existence of the model effect, while a Bayes factor inferior to 1/10 will be considered as a strong evidence for its absence. A Bayes factor above 3 or below 1/3 will be seen as a moderate evidence, while a Bayes factor between 3 and 1/3 will not allow for any conclusion [38].

Each of these ANOVAs has a different goal:

- The first one applied to the "speech only" condition will primarily test the interaction RT x group, to determine whether NH and HI listeners are affected differently by the temporal smearing of speech caused by reverberation. This will allow to answer the hypothesis 1.
- The second one applied to the "noise only" condition, will investigate the interaction RT x group x modulation type, to see whether HI and NH listeners are differently affected by the decrease of dip listening benefit caused by reverberation. This will allow to answer the hypothesis 2.
- The third one applied to the "speech + noise" condition will look at the interaction RT x group, to see whether HI and NH listeners are affected differently by reverberation when it is applied on both sources. This will allow to answer the hypothesis 3-1.
- The fourth and fifth ones, applied to the "speech + noise" condition will look at the interaction RT x noise for the NH and HI listeners separately, to determine whether the dip listening decrease is significant when reverberation is applied to speech and noise for both groups. This will allow to answer hypothesis 3-2-a and 3-2-b.

To deepen our analysis, post hoc tests will also be performed. To answer the hypothesis 1-1, Bayesian repeated measures t-tests will compare the intelligibility scores between RT = 0 s and the other RTs, for each group of listeners and each noise modulation. This will allow to determine the lowest RT at which each group is first affected. To answer the hypothesis 1-2, Bayesian repeated measures t-tests will compare the score difference between RT = 0 s and RT = 1.5 s between groups. This will allow to determine whether HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at high RTs.

In addition to these tests, a supplementary ANOVA will be applied across the three application of reverberation ("speech only", "noise only", "speech+noise"). This test will look at

the effects of the hearing loss and the application of reverberation. Since these two effects are near certain, this ANOVA will act as a form of positive control, and is not included in the analysis plan.

(ii) Sampling plan

With a Bayesian analysis, statistical power is not as much a problem as it is with a frequentist analysis. Indeed, since Bayesian tests can provide evidence for the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis, it is possible to accumulate participants until the Bayes factor reaches a critical value or until a preset maximum number of participants has been reached [39]. Here, it was decided to do Bayes Factor Design Analysis [40], more specifically a SBF+maxN design. The objective of these power analyses was to determine the probability to obtain misleading evidence or inconclusive results. It was done with a Monte Carlo method [41].

Based on previous results, a Monte Carlo analysis was done only for the hypothesis 3-1. Data are lacking to make any accurate power analysis for the other hypotheses. The intelligibility scores in the various conditions were randomly generated from Gaussian distributions having the means and standard deviations measured by Harris and Swenson (1990) [16] in RAUs. The Bayesian ANOVAs were then applied with the minimum number of listeners (16 NH and 16 HI listeners). The number of listeners was then raised progressively (two by two, one supplementary listener for each group), until a Bayes Factor superior to 3 or inferior to 1/3 was reached for the RT x group interaction, or until the maximum number of listeners (64 listeners) was reached. This procedure was repeated 2000 times.

It was estimated that, with a minimum of 32 listeners and a maximum of 64 listeners (in total, NH + HI), there was a probability of 0.82 to confirm the absence of a RT x group interaction, a probability of 0.16 to prove the existence of an interaction (contradicting our hypothesis) and a probability of 0.02 to reach the maximum number of listeners without being able to conclude. If the maximum number of listeners is reached, there is a probability of 0.47 that the Bayes Factor points in the hypothesized direction (that is to say, that the Bayes Factor is inferior to 1). The mean number of listeners necessary to reach a conclusive Bayes Factor was estimated at 36.

Based on these analyses, it was decided to test a maximum of 64 listeners (32 for each group). First a minimum of 32 listeners will be tested (16 per group). The data will then be analysed. New listeners will then be tested until the maximum number of listeners is reached, or until a Bayes factor above 3 or below 1/3 is reached for all the following tests:

- The RT x group interaction in the "speech only" condition hypothesis 1.
- The RT x group x noise modulation in the "noise only" condition hypothesis 2.
- The RT x group interaction in the "speech + noise" condition hypothesis 3-1.

Table 4 presents the design for the proposed study. The sampling plan column was removed so that the table was more legible. In summary, for the sampling plan of this experiment, we aimed to have a probability of 0.8 to detect an absence of RT x group interaction. It was only possible to study hypothesis 3-1 due to a lack of pre-existing data. Artificial data was randomly generated based on the literature. 2000 simulations were run to calculate the statistical power, based on a SBF+maxN method [40]. Bayes Factor of 3 and 1/3 were chosen as thresholds to detect presence and absence of effect. It was estimated that, with a minimum of 32 listeners and a maximum of 64 listeners, there was a probability of 0.82 to detect an absence of RT x group interaction.

Table 4: Design table.

Question	Hypothesis	Analysis	Interpretation given different outcomes
Are HI listeners more affected by reverberation when it is applied only on speech?	1: the temporal smearing of the speech caused by reverberation impairs more HI listeners than NH listeners.	Repeated measures mixed design Bayesian ANOVA. Objective: determine whether HI listeners are more impaired by reverberation on speech, by studying the group x RT interaction.	If $BF > 3$ for the RT x group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis 1 and proceed with the post hoc tests. If $BF < 1/3$: there is evidence for the absence of a group x RT interaction. Hypothesis 1 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.
Are HI listeners more affected by reverberation when it is applied only on speech?	1-1: the temporal smearing of the target speech impairs intelligibility at lower levels of reverberation for HI listeners compared to NH listeners (that is to say HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at low RTs).	Bayesian t-tests to do pairwise comparisons between RT = 0 s and the other RTs for each group and noise condition. Objective: determine the lowest RT at which each group is first affected.	RT threshold: lowest RT for which there is proof for a score difference compared to the RT = 0.15 s condition. It will indicate that the listeners are affected by reverberation above this particular RT. If the HI group has a lower RT threshold than the NH group: we claim full support for 1-1. If the HI group has a higher BF than the NH group for the same RT threshold: we claim partial support for 1-1. If there is no RT threshold ($BF < 1/3$ for all comparisons): hypothesis 1-1 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$ before reaching a minimum RT threshold: nothing can be concluded.
Are HI listeners more affected by reverberation when it is applied only on speech?	1-2: at high levels of reverberation, HI listeners are more impaired than NH listeners by the temporal smearing of the speech (that is to say, HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at high RTs).	Bayesian t-test to compare the difference in intelligibility scores between RT = 0 s and RT = 1.5 s for both groups and noise conditions. Objective: determine whether HI listeners are more affected than NH listeners at high RTs.	If there is a difference between the difference in intelligibility scores for both groups ($BF > 3$): we claim full support for 1-2. If $BF < 1/3$: the magnitude of the effect is similar for both groups. Hypothesis 1-2 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.

<p>Are HI listeners affected differently by reverberation when it is applied only to modulated noise?</p>	<p>2: reverberation affects the dip listening benefit more for NH listeners than for HI listeners.</p>	<p>Repeated measure mixed design Bayesian ANOVAs. Objective: determine whether both groups are affected differently by the dip listening decrease, by studying the group x RT x noise interaction.</p>	<p>If $BF > 3$ for the RT x noise x group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis 2 and proceed with the post hoc tests. If $BF < 3$: hypothesis 2 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.</p>
<p>Are HI and NH listeners affected differently by reverberation when it is applied to noise and speech?</p>	<p>3-1: the overall (monaural) effect of reverberation impairs HI listeners as much as NH listeners.</p>	<p>Repeated measure mixed design Bayesian ANOVA. Objective: determine whether HI listeners are more impaired by reverberation on speech and noise, by studying the RT x group interaction.</p>	<p>If $BF < 1/3$ for the RT x group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis 3-1. If $BF > 3$: hypothesis 3-1 is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.</p>
<p>In the case of NH listeners, does the dip listening decrease have a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise?</p>	<p>3-2-a: In the case of NH listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise.</p>	<p>Repeated measure mixed design Bayesian ANOVA with the results of the NH listeners. Objective: determine whether the dip listening decrease is significant when reverberation is applied to speech and noise, by studying the RT x noise interaction.</p>	<p>If $BF > 3$ for the RT x group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis for 3-2-a. If $BF < 1/3$: hypothesis 3-2-a is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.</p>

In the case of HI listeners, does the dip listening decrease have a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise?	3-2-b: In the case of HI listeners the dip listening decrease has a significant effect on intelligibility when reverberation is applied to speech and noise.	Repeated measure mixed design Bayesian ANOVA with the results of the HI listeners. Objective: determine whether the dip listening decrease is significant when reverberation is applied to speech and noise, by studying the RT x noise interaction.	If $BF > 3$ for the RT x group interaction: we claim full support for hypothesis for 3-2-b. If $BF < 1/3$: hypothesis 3-2-b is rejected. If $1/3 < BF < 3$: nothing can be concluded.
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Data availability

All data, test programs and data analysis scripts will be provided on the Zotero full open source platform. The speech material is under copyright from the company Hörtech gGmbH and cannot be provided.

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